

PRACTICES AND ADHERENCE TO ANTIBIOTIC USE OF BARANGAY SALVACION, BAYOMBONG, NUEVA VIZCAYA

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ABSTRACT

Antibiotic resistance remains a critical global health threat, as declared by the World Health Organization, due to its implications for public health, food security, and development. The rise in antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is primarily linked to inappropriate antibiotic usage and poor adherence to prescribed treatments. In rural areas such as Barangay Salvacion, these behaviors are influenced by a range of contextual factors. This study examines local antibiotic use and adherence practices to create effective health education interventions. Employing a qualitative-descriptive design guided by Nola Pender's Health Belief Model, data were gathered through interviews with 11 residents and analyzed using Braun and Clarke's Thematic Analysis. Findings revealed that while many residents obtain antibiotics through pharmacies following physician consultations, others rely on unauthorized sources, such as sari-sari stores or leftover medications at home. Particularly, public awareness and knowledge gaps regarding antibiotic use influence the residents to engage in self-medication, premature discontinuation of treatment regimens, disposal practices, and retention of unused supplies. Additionally, residents often depend on social media and informal networks for health information, which perpetuates misinformation. Only a few participants reported full adherence to prescribed regimens or awareness of the risks of resistance due to early discontinuation or dose alterations. These key findings guided the creation of targeted health education materials distributed within the community. Hence, these results suggest stricter implementation of antibiotic distribution regulation and safe disposal, along with widespread public awareness campaigns in communities to address misinformation by providing clear and correct information from healthcare providers and trusted sources.

Keywords: *Antibiotic adherence, Antibiotic resistance, Antimicrobial resistance (AMR), community-based intervention, public health education, self-medication, unauthorized antibiotic distribution*

INTRODUCTION

The World Health Organization (WHO) has declared antibiotic resistance one of the biggest threats to global health, food security, and development (WHO, 2020). This resistance endangers healthcare systems, especially for vulnerable patients where next-line antibiotics are lacking. (Dadgostar, 2019). The declining effectiveness of antibiotics highlights the fragility of our health, economic, and security systems worldwide (MacPherson, 2021). Easy access to antibiotics without prescriptions worsens resistance, and unclear treatment guidelines lead to excessive use.

Antibiotics are drugs that treat bacterial illnesses in forms of pills, capsules, or liquids. Topical applications include lotions, sprays, or ointments for the skin. Eye ointments and eardrops are also available, as well as IV (NLM, 2022). With the progressive and modernizing development of antibiotics, infectious and fatal diseases can now be treated (Hutchings, et al, 2019). At present, 27 new antibiotics are being developed against priority pathogens, and to combat the escalating incidence of AMR due to stagnation of developments (WHO, 2022).

Improper antibiotic disposal is a key contributor to environmental antibiotic resistance (Auta et al., 2019). In the Philippines, many families either retain unused antibiotics or dispose of them improperly due to the lack of return programs or disposal guidelines (Salazar et al.). Proper usage and adherence to antibiotics are crucial to avoid resistance (Chapman, 2018), as non-compliance significantly contributes to the growing issue of antimicrobial resistance (Gasson et al., 2018).

Antibiotic resistance is driven by misuse, including self-medication and irregular dosing (Wall, 2019; CDC, 2022). It's worsened by poor antibiotic recognition, misconceptions, and limited healthcare access (Karuniawati, 2020; Gunasekera et al., 2022; Esteves et al., 2023). Non-prescribed antibiotics like amoxicillin are commonly bought, and practices such as sharing or stopping early are widespread (Irawati, 2019). This is a global issue, worsened by poor regulation and knowledge (Wang, 2022; Belachew et al., 2021).

In the Philippines, studies show 66% prevalence of self-medication (Robredo et al., 2022), premature discontinuation of antibiotics (Barber et al., 2017), and a knowledge gap based on income (Vidad et al., 2022). In rural Mozambique, people identify antibiotics by color and share them (Cambaco et al., 2020). Globally, ABR is rising due to poor-quality antibiotics, lax regulations, and misuse in agriculture (Chokshi, 2019). Despite limited local studies, improper practices like antibiotic sharing, using herbal remedies, and buying from sari-sari stores persist. Thus, a community-based approach and education are crucial to addressing informal antibiotic use (Barber et al., 2017; Robredo et al., 2022).

Statement of the Problem

This study explored the practices and adherence of residents of Barangay Salvacion, Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya on antibiotic use during the first semester of School Year 2023-2024, and answered the following questions:

1. What are the residents' practices about antibiotics?
2. How do residents adhere to antibiotic use?
3. What health education information can be developed based on the study's findings?

METHODOLOGY

This study used a qualitative-descriptive research design to explore the antibiotic practices and adherence of residents in Baranga Salvacion, Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya. The qualitative approach focused on understanding individual perceptions through semi-structured interviews, while the descriptive aspect systematically interpreted these perceptions to highlight community behaviors.

This research was conducted in Barangay Salvacion, a central barangay in Bayombong Nueva Vizcaya. Its proximity to commercial centers and the Rural Health Unit made it strategic location for investigating health behaviors in a diverse population. A total of 11 participants were selected through criterion sampling, all of whom were aged 19-59 years old, belonged to low-income households (below ₱ 10, 481/month), had used antibiotics in the past 6 months, had lived in the barangay for at least 6 months. Those who did not meet the criteria, including individuals aged 18 and below or 60 and above, were excluded.

The study used a semi-structured interview guide to collect qualitative data. This format allowed participants to express their experiences freely, while still enabling the researchers to explore specific topics such as access to antibiotics, antibiotic use practices, adherence to prescriptions, and awareness of antibiotic resistance. It begins by investigating how participants obtain antibiotics, including whether they access them through formal channels like consulting physicians and purchasing from pharmacies, or through informal means such as buying from local sari-sari stores. The succeeding set of questions examines the practices regarding antibiotic consumption, particularly frequency, reasons for antibiotic use and whether the full course of treatment is completed. It also looks into behaviors like self-medication, prematurely stopping antibiotics when symptoms disappear, and sharing leftover antibiotics—practices that may contribute to misuse. The final section addresses participants' awareness of the consequences of improper antibiotic use. It probes their understanding of antibiotic resistance and whether they believe their personal behaviors may contribute to this global health threat. Overall, the interview guide is designed to gather comprehensive qualitative data on the patterns and perceptions of antibiotic use in the community.

Validation of the guide questions was sought from experts in the field. The experts sought are registered nurses and have been exposed to community nursing practice. The first validator is a graduate of Saint Mary's University (SMU), with a Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) degree, and has been a Philippine registered nurse since 2011. Additionally, the validator has six months of clinical experience and has served as a nursing instructor for Community Health nursing-related nursing experience since 2022. The second validator is also a graduate of SMU with a BSN degree and has been a registered nurse in the Philippines since 2009. Likewise, the second validator has over ten years of clinical experience, including exposure to the community nursing practice as a "nurse to the barrio" for six months and served as a nursing instructor for Community Health Nursing related nursing experience for a year now.

The researchers coordinated with the Barangay Chairman of Salvacion to conduct house-to-house visits and recruit qualified participants. After explaining the study and obtaining informed consent, interviews were conducted in private and secure settings. A validated semi-structured interview guide was used, and responses were audio-recorded with the participants' permission. Data collection took place over two weeks during first semester of the School Year 2023-2024, with ethical standards and participant confidentiality strictly observed.

Interviews were transcribed and anonymized using participant codes (e.g. R1, R2, etc.). Data were analyzed using Braun and Clarke's Thematic Analysis method; familiarization with data, coding of key statements, identification of emerging themes, reviewing and refining themes, defining themes, and writing the report. An inductive approach was applied, and researchers used constant comparison across transcripts to ensure consistency and reliability.

The study was approved by the Saint Mary's University Research Ethics Board (SMUREB), ensuring adherence to ethical research standards. Informed consent was obtained from all participants after explaining the purpose of the study, procedures, and their voluntary right to withdraw at any time. To protect participant privacy, all personal data were anonymized and securely stored. Audio recordings from the interviews were saved in a hard drive, accessible only to the researchers and their adviser. These data will be kept for two years and will permanently be deleted after a 2-year archiving period.

Foreseeable risks such as invasion of privacy, time inconvenience, and concerns over data storage were minimized by conducting interviews at a time and place convenient for participants,

explaining the security measures for storing data, and ensuring confidentiality throughout the study. No participants experienced harm or discomfort during the process.

The study benefits the residents by increasing awareness of proper antibiotic use and the risks of misuse, such as antibiotic resistance. Findings were shared with the community through printed educational materials and presentations, aiming to provide their health practices and promote safer use of antibiotics in the future. No conflicts of interest were reported by the researchers.

The Health Education Information (HEI) material was produced in the form of a pamphlet and poster. These were then distributed among the residents in the community, at the Barangay Health Center, Bayombong Municipal Health Office, Solano Rural Health Unit, University Clinic, and SMU-affiliated hospitals including Region II Trauma and Medical Center, Nueva Vizcaya Provincial Hospital, Medical Mission Group Hospital and Salubris Medical Center.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Section 1. Practices on Antibiotic Use

This section focuses on antibiotic use practice, particularly antibiotic acquisition and use. It explores the disparities among 11 respondents in accessing antibiotics, across diverse healthcare systems, socioeconomic status, and geographical regions. This section also considers the residents' improper antibiotic use and disposal, providing insight into public awareness and knowledge gaps on antibiotic resistance despite existing awareness campaigns. Finally, it investigates the role of social circles and digital, non-professional sources in shaping individuals' understanding and behaviors around antibiotic use.

1.1 Access to Antibiotics

Ten of the residents stated that they obtain antibiotics through pharmacies, which are authorized by dispensing such medications. A response from R8 was, "*Depende, pag galing akong doktor [doon ako bumibili]. Pero kapag kailangan ko na [ng antibiotic], diretso akong botika*" ("It depends. If I've been to the doctor, I buy it from there. But if I need antibiotics, I go directly to the pharmacy"). This suggests that pharmacies remain the primary and most accessible source of antibiotics, indicating a positive trend as pharmacies are more likely to provide regulated antibiotics. Community pharmacists are significant in ensuring proper antibiotic dispensing, patient education regarding antibiotic use, and reduction of antibiotic misuse among the community as community pharmacies are the top dispensers of antibiotics, implementing antimicrobial stewardship measures to optimize antibiotic use, minimize unnecessary prescriptions, and educate the public on responsible medication use (Rusic, et al., 2021).

Meanwhile, eight residents shared that they obtain antibiotics through a clinical visit. R4 stated that "*Kapag bumibili ako ng antibiotics, usually bibili lang naman ako kapag prinescribe ito ng doctor*" ("Whenever I buy antibiotics, I usually only buy them when a doctor prescribes them"). Moreover, R5 has stated, "*Hindi naman ako basta basta bumibili ng antibiotic ng walang reseta ng doktor*" ("I don't just buy antibiotics without a doctor's prescription"). These responses indicate a reliance on professional guidance from doctors and nurses, which reflect a relatively high level of awareness regarding proper antibiotic use (Said, 2025).

Nevertheless, there are three residents who reported that they obtain their antibiotics from small retail shops such as sari-sari stores. As R1 says, "*Meron po [mga nagtitinda], 6 pesos sa sari-sari*"

store. *Ako rin ang titinda noon, like amox (Amoxicillin).*” “*Sa sari-sari store ko nabili yung gamot ko sa pigsas ko for 7 days,*” (“There are [vendors], 6 pesos at the sari-sari store... I would also sell it then, like amox (Amoxicillin). I bought medicine for my boil for 7 days at the sari-sari store.”). This suggests that antibiotics are informally available outside of pharmacies, raising concerns about proper regulation and prescription requirements leading to improper self-medication and antibiotic misuse. Correspondingly, there are existing antibiotic regulation aimed to restrict Over-the-counter (OTC) sales of antibiotics but due to the lack of enforcement, improper usage is still being practiced (Rojop, et al., 2024).

Additionally, one resident reported being unaware of the availability of antibiotics in small retail shops, suggesting limited knowledge about informal sales avenues. They stated, “*Wala, wala akong nababalitaan na ganun kasi hindi ako pamilyar na nagbebenta sila ng prescribed drugs*” (“Nothing, I haven’t heard of that because I’m not familiar with them selling prescribed drugs”). Furthermore, this emphasizes the need to increase public knowledge about both legal and illegal distribution channels. It also supports the necessity of implementing policies aimed at strengthening regulatory frameworks and improving the effectiveness of awareness campaigns. Educational interventions within communities are crucial to enhance antibiotic literacy, particularly concerning the risks of improper use and the importance of obtaining medications from authorized outlets. This prevents the widespread practice of antibiotic self-medication stemming from over-the-counter access, weak regulatory enforcement, and limited consumer understanding of the consequences of improper usage (Corpuz et al., 2025).

1.2 Public Awareness and Knowledge Gaps on Antibiotic Resistance

This theme assesses the general public’s understanding of antibiotic resistance and its consequences, evaluating the effectiveness of existing campaigns and programs in addressing these gaps. Four residents acknowledged that the non-completion of the full course of antibiotic regimen can result in an increase in dosage or stronger antibiotics. One resident narrates, “*Kapag hindi maganda yung paggamit, pwedeng hindi maging mabisa yung gamot, kaya kukuha na naman ng mas malakas na gamot, hanggang sa maubos na, naniniwala na po ako doon*” (“If the medication is not used properly, it might not be effective, so you end up needing stronger medication, and it goes on until it’s all used up. I believe in that now”). Another resident adds, “*Yun [Antibiotic resistance] ba yung kapag hindi mo natapos yung nireseta sayo ng doctor e pwedeng hindi mag take effect yung gamot na gagamitin or mas kailangan ng mas mataas na dosage para mapatay yung bacteria*” (“Is antibiotic resistance when you don’t finish the prescribed medication, and it might not work, or you might need a higher dosage to kill the bacteria?”). Misuse and incomplete dosages are the primary causes of resistance. Misinformation, such as public misconceptions that stronger antibiotics are required when symptoms persist or that stopping medication early is harmless, are widespread (WHO, 2020).

Meanwhile, six respondents were unaware of antibiotic resistance. Particularly, some shared that, “*Ngayon ko lang nalaman na ganon pala dapat na kailangan pala tapusin yung binigay sayo*” (“I just learned now that you’re supposed to finish the medication given to you”) and “*Parang wala naman [eppekto ng pagtigil ng pag-take ng antibiotic].*” (“It seems like there’s no effect [from stopping the antibiotic]). These gaps suggest an urgent need for public health education on antibiotic resistance and proper adherence to treatment regimens. Many do not understand the mechanisms of resistance resulting to self-medication, improper dosage adjustments, and early discontinuation of antibiotics, all of which contribute to resistance (Nasr, et al., 2021). Similarly, rural residents often relied on traditional knowledge or community-shared practices, leading to inappropriate antibiotic use (Labi et al., 2019).

Additionally, widespread prevalence of antibiotic consumption without proper medical consultation and prescription among the residents suggests the emergence of antibiotic resistance. Seven residents admitted that they engage in self-medication. One resident stated, "*Nasubukan ko [ang mag-self medicate] ng 7-days dito sa parang pigsa ko [sa kamay]*" (I tried self-medicating for 7 days here for what seemed like a boil on my hand"). This information poses a significant public health concern, as self-medication is an act of improper drug use. For some, self-medication of antibiotics is considered a form of self-care—a good practice as it is convenient and cost-saving (Eltom et al., 2022). Likewise, it is viewed as an act of responsibility for maintaining health. Medications like antibiotics are also considered household goods (Torres, et al., 2020). Moreover, extrinsic factors such as inability to afford a consultation and insufficient public health awareness were identified. (Esteves, et al., 2023).

Six residents reported that they use antibiotics as a secondary regimen or alternative treatment, aside from delaying their regimen based on their symptoms. Some state, "*Mga 2 days after ko magkaubo tsaka ako bumibili [ng antibiotics]*" ("About 2 days after I started coughing, that's when I buy [the antibiotics]"), and "*Nu aguyek kasjay [mag-te-take ng antibiotic]*" ("When I have a cough like that [take the antibiotic]"). This indicates that some of the residents take a reactionary rather than preventive approach, where they delay antibiotic use instead of seeking immediate medical advice. This causes the development of antibiotic-resistant pathogens which are associated with further resistance, and increased susceptibility to infection (Bonine, et al., 2019). Furthermore, this practice reflects a misunderstanding of the role of antibiotics, as they are often perceived as a general cure rather than being pathogen-specific. Hence, a healthcare provider must identify the specific pathogen causing the illness as certain antibiotics are effective only against bacterial classifications (Werth, 2025).

In the context of the social factors that affect the utilization of antibiotics, familial, cultural, and societal norms were considered in addition to social beliefs regarding illness and recovery. Primarily, five out of eleven residents reported sharing leftover antibiotics with friends or family members who need them. Particularly, some of the respondents stated that, "*mga kaibigan ko kapag may nasugat ganon [nagbibigay ng natirang antibiotic]*" ("I give my friend the leftover antibiotics when they have a wound"), "*Oo [nagbibigay sa iba ng mga tira-tirang antibiotics] pag kailangan nila.*" (Yes, I give leftover antibiotics to the others if they need it"). This practice is highly problematic, as it promotes the use of antibiotics without medical supervision and prescription, leading to potentially ineffective treatment. Patients re-used previous medical prescriptions to buy antibiotics (Quebral, 2022). Additionally, sharing antibiotics also increases the likelihood of antibiotic resistance either due to non-completion of the full course or incorrect antibiotic medication for a specific illness. Hence, there is a cultural/social component in which individuals feel responsible for helping others by sharing medication rather than advising them to seek medical attention.

The same five residents who reported that they share antibiotics also admitted that they keep a residual stock intended for future use, but did not specify whether for personal use or sharing. "*Oo meron [nai-stock na gamot], yung amoxicillin,*" ("Yes, I have [stocked medicine], the amoxicillin"), "*Adda agas na dyay mother ko, 1 pad nga antibiotic, agalaak ton idyay nu adda sakit ko.*" ("My mother has medicine, one pad of antibiotics. I will take it when I get sick"). This indicates non-compliance with prescribed antibiotic courses, as proper antibiotic use requires completing the full treatment even if symptoms improve. Common excuses for stopping adherence to prescribed courses is forgetfulness and feeling better after a few days of usage, encouraging patient education to enhance adherence to prescribed antibiotic courses (Almohani et al., 2022). Additionally, some individuals store unused antibiotics and reuse them for future illnesses such as when they feel new symptoms (Almehmadi, 2024).

In contrast, there is only one resident who stated that they do not share antibiotics with other people, when he/she stated, *"hindi po ako nag shshare sa ibang tao"* ("I don't share with other people"). This indicates that most people do not recognize the dangers of sharing antibiotics, which suggests a need for targeted public health campaigns that emphasize the dangers of misuse and resistance development (Almohammed et al., 2022).

Since antibiotics are considered regulated medications, the method of disposal is as crucial as dispensing because it can serve as a method of access for others. There were three residents who reported, *"Tinatapon na namin [yung mga hindi nauubos]"* ("We just throw away the unused ones"), *"Hindi na [gagamitin yung natirang gamot]."* ("The leftover medicine won't be used anymore"). Despite these responses, this practice may not be environmentally safe, since throwing the unused antibiotics, either in the trash or flushing them, could contribute to environmental contamination and antibiotic resistance (Kaur, et al., 2020). In the Philippines, while some residents claimed to return unused antibiotics to pharmacies or health facilities, a significant number admitted to discarding them in household trash or flushing them, suggesting that without clear disposal policies and accessible medication take-back programs, improper disposal remains a common practice (Salazar, et al., 2021). Although most of them had received instructions on how to take them from medical personnel, there was a noticeable lack of knowledge on the disposal of antibiotics (Khabara et al., 2024).

A minority of people adopt safe disposal techniques such as returning unwanted antibiotics to pharmacies or health care facilities. In many underdeveloped nations, including the Philippines, a lack of systematic disposal rules contributes to extensive environmental pollution, as unwanted antibiotics frequently wind up in landfill garbage or sewage systems, creating a reservoir of resistant organisms in the natural environment, and increasing the AMR epidemic on an ecological scale (Auta et al., 2019). Proper medication disposal is influenced by factors such as convenience, access to collection points, education, and gender. Globally, many households store unused or expired medications due to beliefs about future use, limited access, or uncertainty about disposal methods (Rogowska et al., 2022).

1.3 Social Circles and Digital Non-professional Data as Sources of Health Information

This investigates the influence of personal networks and online platforms with regard to antibiotic consumption behaviors. One resident stated *"Kase sabi nila [family and friends], malakas daw, kaya iniwasan namin yung side effect"* ("Because they said, it's strong, that's why we're avoiding the side effects"), pertaining to the potential organ damage due to antibiotic use. The same resident reported that they relied on online platforms as a source of health information, stating that, *"Nanood kase ako kay Dr. Ong, sabi nya, pwede naming gamot ang amox para sa pigs, hindi ko naman iinumun yung kapag hindi ko napanood yun."* ("I watched Dr. Ong, he stated that amox can be used for carbuncles, I wouldn't take it if I didn't watch it").

The influence of personal networks and online platforms on antibiotic consumption behaviors is well-documented in public health research. People tend to trust the advice of relatives and friends over professional medical guidance. This social reinforcement of misinformation contributes to antibiotic resistance and adverse health outcomes (Lu, et al., 2021). In the Philippines, many rely entirely on non-professional advice from social media influencers and unverified health websites, emphasizing the need for community-based health education and stronger digital literacy programs to ensure the public access to reliable medical information and practices responsible for antibiotic use (Medina & Tingson, 2019).

This aligns with the response of another resident who stated, *“Dati [tinatapos ang prescribed days] pero ngayon kapag okay na tinitigil na kasi nga inaalala ngayon yung [antibiotic] tatama sa kidney”* (“Before [used to finish the prescribed antibiotic course] but now if it’s already okay I stop because I’m worried now that [antibiotics] will harm the kidneys”), referring to the belief that antibiotics can cause organ damage, leading them to avoid use based on non-professional advice. The spread of misinformation, particularly regarding antibiotic effectiveness and safety, was reported to be linked to increased antibiotic misuse (Chou, et al., 2020).

Section 2. Adherence to Antibiotic Medication

This section addresses key concepts associated with the residents’ adherence to antibiotic medication, particularly if they follow the prescribed regimen or deviate from it. This explores the factors that influence their commitment to abide by the advice of a medical professional. In contrary, it analyzes self-adjustment of antibiotic prescription, describing the factors that influence an individual’s decision to alter the dosage and pattern of their antibiotic treatment without regard to the prescribed guidelines.

2.1 Knowledge of Antibiotic Use

Primarily, comprehension of adherence to antibiotic regimens is a key contributor to how the residents adhere to their prescriptions. Four residents demonstrated that they completed the full course as prescribed by their doctors. One stated, *“Hindi ako [tunitigil magtake] as long na hindi pa tapos yung days [ng prescription] na binigay sa akin, nagtetake pa rin ako [ng antibiotics]”* (“I do not [stop taking] as long as the days are not yet finished [of prescription] that were given to me, I still continue to take [antibiotics]”), and another confirmed that, *“Oo kasi yun naman yung nakalagay sa nireseta ng doctor. [tinatapos ng seven days].”* (“Yes, because that is what the doctor prescribed. [Completed in 7 days]”). This indicates that there is a good level of awareness regarding the necessity of finishing the regimen to ensure the effectiveness of antibiotics and prevent resistance. Understanding the necessity of finishing antibiotics translates into consistent adherence, revealing a significant correlation between knowledge, attitude, and practices (Dhivya et al., 2024). *“Ahm, yes oo kasi sabi po ng doctor tapusin daw po.”* (“Ahm, yes yes because the doctor said finish it”), one resident stated. However, with only four of the residents following this practice, there remains a gap in adherence among many respondents. Even though individuals know the proper way of using antibiotics, they still refuse to adhere and believe that antibiotic resistance only occurs in other nations (Muflih et al., 2021).

Likewise, the same respondents also reported strictly following their doctor’s prescriptions, indicating that a portion of the sample population sought proper medical consultation prior to obtaining a prescription. Specifically, the residents stated that, *“Wen, ajay one day ket 3 times a day [nu agtake]”* (“Yes, In one day 3x a day [if taken]”), *“Actually lagi kong sinusunod kung ano yung mga nakalagay sa reseta na binibigay sa akin.”* (“Actually I always follow what’s in the prescription that was given to me”). However, given that this percentage is below half of the majority, it signifies that many individuals may either misunderstand or disregard medical instructions, which may lead to inconsistent antibiotic use. Additionally, there were two residents who recognized the potential consequences of antibiotic misuse in relation to improper adherence to antibiotic courses, which is consistent with the findings under public awareness of antibiotic resistance mentioned in the previous section. This implies that the misuse due to the fear of its side effects made them resort to self-adjustment of dosages, suggesting a tailored health education to advocate for prevention of antibiotic resistance (Gebregziabher et al. (2024).

Only one resident revealed that “*Kapag bumibili ako ng antibiotics usually bibili lang naman ako kapag prinescribe ito ng doctor.*” (“If I buy antibiotics usually, I only buy when it’s prescribed by the doctor”). This implies that there are still individuals who take antibiotics without prior professional consultation, which may consequently lead to misuse, incorrect dosage, or development of antibiotic resistance (Tajali et al., 2024).

2.2 Self-Adjustment of Antibiotic Prescription

This explores unauthorized changes to prescribed dosage and regimen completion. Only one resident explicitly states, “*Minsan hindi ko na binibigay, lalo kapag dala-dalawa na, [kaya] hindi ko na binibigay lahat*” (Sometimes I do not give anymore, especially if there are two already, [that’s why] I do not give everything anymore”). The existence of misunderstanding of antibiotic dosing significantly reduces drug efficacy and contributes to either treatment failure or resistance. In fact, deviations from prescribed regimens, including dosage and schedule alteration increases the risk of developing an infection resistant to antibiotics (Reiner-Benaim et al., 2022). This shows how easily treatment effectiveness can be compromised and that enhanced patient education and strict dosing adherence are necessary to avoid the development of resistance and to maintain therapeutic effectiveness.

Apart from altering the dosage, six respondents reported not completing their prescriptions. Some stopped taking antibiotics once they felt better, while others discontinued due to concerns about side effects. Only one resident claims, “*Hindi ako [tumitigil magtake] as long na hindi pa tapos yung days [ng prescription] na binigay sa akin, nagtetake pa rin ako [ng antibiotics]*” (“I do not [stop taking] as long as the days are not yet finished [of prescription] that was given to me, I still continue to take [antibiotics]”). Some factors affecting adherence are forgetfulness, premature relief of symptoms, and adverse side effects that reduced treatment efficacy and led to the emergence of resistant bacterial strains, increasing the risk of recurrent infections (Endashaw, et al., 2022).

Section 3. Kamalayan tungkol sa Antibiotic Resistance

The Health Education Information (HEI) material was entitled “Kamalayan tungkol sa Antibiotic Resistance,” which directly translates to ‘Antibiotic Resistance Awareness.’ The contents were based on the significant findings of this study.

It delivers a clear message focused on antibiotics and the risks of improper use, particularly the growing threat of antibiotic resistance. It begins by defining antibiotics and antibiotic resistance to establish context, then outline proper and improper usage, consequences of resistance, and prevention strategies. It also addresses key issues such as proper disposal of leftover antibiotics and common misconceptions, such as high prevalence of self-medication (Uddin, et al., 2021).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

Several important factors that contribute to the use and adherence of antibiotics by residents are emphasized in this study. Although most people acquire antibiotics from authorized sources, the ongoing circulation of antibiotics among non-accredited informal sellers is believed to contribute to the misuse. Self-treatment which gives way to misinformation and recommendations of social and digital networks amplify this situation. While some participants adhere to prescriptions properly, non-compliance is widespread, influenced by misconceptions, fear of side effects and inadequate

duration of therapy—all of which play an important role in the expanding problem of antibiotic resistance.

To combat these challenges, the study recommends the use of Health Education Information (HEI) materials such as pamphlets to support the safe use of antibiotics. The educational materials should teach about the necessity of adhering to prescription, risks of antibiotic misuse and the correct methods of disposing antibiotics. The research underlines the necessity for specific educational programs and community-based treatment programs.

Recommendations

The study offers several practical evidence-based suggestions for better antibiotic use. Reinforcement of public awareness about the dangers of self-medication prescription and disposal promotes responsible habits towards antibiotic use. Tighter prescription-only selling in authorized shops should be implemented, but in a phased manner of increased awareness. Health Education Information (HEI) pamphlets as one type of educational resource may help, given widely distributed by clinics, schools, and communities. Local health units should improve their community outreach programs and encourage consultation to decrease antibiotic acquisition from informal sources. The academic community should promote antibiotic education through curriculum inclusion and student participation in public health initiatives. The proposed actions represent useful measures which match study results to support existing antibiotic stewardship initiatives.

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